
AN EXAMINATION OF THE CONCEPT OF LAW AND JUSTICE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

In a civilized society, law and justice play an important role in shaping the society towards achieving the standard goals. The standard as set out by the society be it civilized or uncivilized for the attainment of certain goals in line with the law and justice of a particular State must correspond to the norms, values and behaviors of a given society. Refusing to abide by what the law says, justice in any given case will not be attainable. This paper seeks to examine the concept of law and justice in Nigeria. This paper focuses on the relationship between law and justice with practical situation under the Nigerian context. This paper adopts doctrinal legal research by analyzing primary and secondary sources of legal materials. The paper found as follows: Under Military regime, the highest law of the land is the Military Decree which does not accord a citizen right to express himself unlike, in the Democratic state. Doctrine of separation of power is not adhered to under Military, Section 4(8) of the 1999 Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria subjected the legislative powers to the jurisdiction of the courts thereby creating vacuum in the dispensation of Justice. This paper recommends that: Nigerians should follow the dictate of the democratic system of government. Separation of power should maintain particularly; the Legislature shall not be subjected to the legislative arms of government unless with cogent and compelling reasons. Nigerian should enact laws to achieve justice for Nigerians, rigorous provisions should be amended.

1.1 Introduction

Law and Justice, these two concepts are sometime misleading in their actual understanding by people and societies. Legal and political theories since the time of Plato have dwelled of contemplating whether to justice is part of law or a pronouncement of the law by judges, tribunals and the courts.¹ The relationship of law and justice has always been an area of concern and debates. Exploring philosophical approaches underpinned the study of law and justice in in Nigeria. Relationship between law and justice is to highlight the intersection of the terms to provide conducive atmosphere in the dispensation of justice in Nigeria. It is better to define law and justice for proper doing justice to the concept at hand.

1.2 Definition of law

Various definitions have been given to the term “law”, in that, law has no universal accepted definition of the word law, it is an abstract. Using common understanding, the word law, sometime is referred to as norms, values, behaviors, rules and regulations. It has been said that, all laws in Nigeria are based on fundamental norm from which they get their validity dis obeying the norms punishment will be invoke.² This definition of law, is in line with the understanding of positivists school of thought. They posited that, law is a command backed by sanction.³ A leading prominent among them is John Austin, he defines law as:

... a command set, either directly or circuitously, by a sovereign individual or body, to a member or members of some independent political society in which his authority is supreme. The sovereign punishes his subjects for violation of his law.⁴

Aquinas T. opined that, “Law is nothing else than a rational ordering of things, which concern the common good; promulgated by whoever is in charged with the care of the community”.⁵ According to Aristotle and Plato, “Law” as the voice of reason”. While, historical school of thought on the other hand, attempted to define the word “law”, as exhibited by Von Savigny as “the expression of the common consciousness of a people”. He suggests that, law was founded by norms, values and behaviors of people in a community, which is rooted to their customs and believes which silently operates, not by arbitrary will of a law giver”.⁶ Sociological approach, on the other hand, prominent among them was Von Ihering, he conceives law as “the sum of the conditions of social life as secured by the power of the state through the means of external compulsion.

The sociological school of thought, emphasizes that, law is the totality of social life which the government established itself through the use of other forces not the government itself but, by employing certain forces such as coercive and full control of resources of the community.

¹. Hakeem Ijaiya and HakeematIjay; *Law-as-a-Mean-e-in-Nigeria*; June 2018 volume 13, Pendacta; number 1 p. 1-9 available at <https://www.google.com> assessed on 10/12/2024 around 12:31 pm.

²The Nigerian Legal System; Learn the Law at Your Own Pace; by Kelechi Alpheaus; Published by Learn Nigerian Law available at www.google.com accessed on the 10/12/2024.

³. <https://www.researchgate.net> “*Law and Justice* “available at www.google.com accessed on the 10/12/2024 around 12: 35 pm.

⁴. Pendacta; *Law-as-a-Mean-e-in-Nigeria*; June 2018 volume 13, number 1; p. 1-9 available at <https://www.google.com> assessed on 10/12/2024 around 12:31 pm.

⁵ Supra; at p. 2.

⁶ Ibid.

According to American Realists Movement, law consists of the rules recognized and acted upon by the courts of justice.

However, Karl Marx had a different view concerning the word law, he opined that, “Law is a superstructure upon economic base”. This definition as stated by Karl Marx suggests that, in every society the rulers are always exploiting the ruled with the abundance of natural resources thereby making the majority poorer.

1.2.1 Definition of Justice

Some defined the word justice, as to start with many things, when placed in an orderly manner could be said to mean just or unjust, not only in laws, institutions or social systems, but some particular actions of many kinds, including decisions, judgments, and imputations.⁷ Justice, is defined as the way in which major social institutions, distributive, fundamental human rights and duties which determines the division of advantages of social co-operation. Some also consider justice, to mean fairness, the original position of equality of treatment between societies in all the sphere of justice. This statement is not the actual historical state of affairs, much less than the primitive position of culture as in line with the examples given of the word justice.⁸

After knowing justice as, justice, to mean fairness, the original position of equality of treatment between societies in all the sphere of justice. It implies the need to adhere of doing justice to one another in any assigned work person or person is expected to be honest in the discharge of a given task.⁹

1.2.2 Philosophical approaches of law and justice in Nigeria

In the understanding of approaches philosophically one should look carefully, what the highest law in Nigeria says, in respect to these two words above. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended, is an embodiment of the collective will and aspirations people of Nigerian, which concerns with all persons and institutions in the state.¹⁰ It is the supreme law of the land, which imparts all other laws validity, in terms of originality, authenticity and enforcement. In effect, any law which is inconsistent with the provisions of the constitution shall be declared as null and void to the extent of its inconsistency.¹¹ What arose from these definitions, it is crystal that, law is the officially enacted rules of conduct backed by the state’s forces enforced penalties for the offenders.¹²

Historically, mankind had tried to suppress the deviant characters through the use of norms and virtues of their societies as in the state of primitive stage and lastly man employed idea of enacting laws. While making inference of social norms which in most cases have religious and social sanction, laws are sometime written and others are unwritten but, the main intent of the law is, by interpretation, of the various provisions relating to day-to-day interaction

⁷ John Rawls; A theory of Justice; (1999) the president and Fellows of Harvard Collage; Library of Congress; United States of America; Cataloging – in Publication Data;p. 9-10.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ . Adebayo A. M. the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended (2012); Princeton; Ikeja Lagos; p.36.

¹¹ . Section 1(3) the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended.

¹² . <https://www.researchgate.net> “Law and Justice “available at www.google.com assessed on the 10/12/2024 around 12: 35 pm.

between one another. Adherence to that, will make societies to live in peace and harmony of one another for the attainments of social justice.¹³

So, the word “justice”, derived its origin from Latin word “*justus*” means that which is just, “righteous”, “right”, “honest”, etc., justice; in its concept is difficult to appreciate under one single concept. Justice, is the legal or philosophical theory by which, fairness is obtainable mostly in courts of law. But, Plato, explained the meaning of it as, the constant performance, of a designed work of a state. Plato, regards justice as a virtue, establishing rational order, with each of the community performing its established role which naturally, disturbing the functions, powers and duties of the other parts of the societies.¹⁴ Plato considers virtues as a factor that, work hand in hand with the law and legalized certain virtues and make others as illegal virtues.¹⁵

Apart from philosophical definitions, thinkers, referred to the word justice, “as wisdom or virtues as Socrates, consider the word to mean. While Aristotle, in trying to define the word justice, defined it, in a wider and narrow sense. The wider definition of justice, includes: moral disposition, inherently inbuilt, which renders individuals to act justly and causes them to behave just. While the narrow meaning of the word “justice” denotes equality or being exact, or even fair in dealings with others. Aristotle, argued that all lawful are fair acts while unlawful acts are unfair.¹⁶ The American philosopher, by name John Rawls while, referring to the concept of justice, states that, justice, means fairness.

1.3 Nature of Law and Justice in Nigeria

In Nigeria, as a sovereign country, with historical antecedent of independence in 1960 and, the nascent democracy in 1999. The Nigerian judges are having difficulty in dispensing justice, this is because judges should operate under stringent provisions of the Constitution of the Country, which was made by the then military. Under Military regime laws of Military are referred to as the “Decree” after taking an Oath by a Military officer to do justice.¹⁷

It is pertinent to note that, military regimes in Nigeria lasted for almost 30 to 45 years of independence. Under military regimes provisions of the constitution particularly, relating to human rights protection was adhere, to some extent, reference to section 5 of the constitution (suspension and modification) Decree No. 107 of 1993.¹⁸ Also section 1 of the Military Government (Supremacy and Enforcement Powers) Decree No.12 1994 which both the two (2) laws hang up matters which the two Decrees covered.¹⁹ To, appreciate that Section1, of the Military Government (Supremacy and Enforcement Powers) Decree No. 12 of 1994 provides:

“No civil proceedings shall lie or be instituted in any court for or on account as far in any act, matter or thing done or purported to be done under pursuant to any Decree or Edict and if such proceedings are instituted before the

¹³.Pendacta; *Law-as-a-Mean-e-in-Nigeria*; June 2018 volume 13, number 1 p. 1-9 available at <https://www.google.com> assessed on 10/12/2024 around 12:31 pm.

¹⁴. Baston University; <https://www.bu.edu>; Plato’s Concept of Justice: An Analysis; available at www.google.com assessed on the 11/12/2024 around 3:00 pm.

¹⁵. Ibid.

¹⁶. Plato and Aristotle; *Definition of Justice, theory and philosophies* <https://study.com> available at www.google.com assessed on the 11/12/2024 around 3:30 pm.

¹⁷Section 5 of the constitution (suspension and modification) Decree No. 107 of 1993

¹⁸Ibid.

¹⁹section 1 of the Military Government (Supremacy and Enforcement Powers) Decree No.12 1994

commencement of this Decree, the proceedings shall be abate, be discharged and made void.”²⁰

By way of analysis, the above laws in their nature and purposes military regime in Nigeria, practicability, of justice in its true sense is absent. Meaning that, most of the exact practice of justice cannot be attainable in Nigerian courts since the laws are made without consultation. In a Democratic State, consultations are the tools of justice before any actions relating to the affairs of a state can be taken.²¹

It simply suggests that, under Military regime in Nigeria, Section 1, of the Military Government (Supremacy and Enforcement Powers) Decree No. 12 of 1994 have ousted the jurisdictions of courts to entertain any matter where it was instituted or otherwise in matters affecting both the Federal and the State Government.²² Where it was instituted without due recourse to the above Section its amount to usurpations by the courts of the legislative powers.

As in the case of A.G of Anambra and A.G of Federation and State v. Okeke²³ where Justice Uwaifo JCA, stated as follows:

“Decree No. 13 of 1984 is an ouster legislation. Once the provisions of a Decree or Constitution ousting the jurisdiction of the courts on any specific matters are clear and unambiguous, the courts are bound to observe and apply them. They are not entitled, even when the ouster has drastic effect on the right of any person, to approach its interpretation by a false or twisted meaning given to it by unacceptable restricted construction”.²⁴

However, the above position of the Nigerian set up during Military era, Nigeria should try as much as possible to allow the practice of the democratic affairs by ensuring the guarantees of individuals rights.²⁵ Ouster clause, in effect, takes another shape by subjecting the rights of Nigerian citizens, to the legislative test of a legislative arm of government. Making deep analysis of Section 6 (3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, it will be inferred that, the authority which Nigerian courts derived cannot be conclusively said it was from the constitution. Since power given under the Constitution could be said to be exercise efficiently.²⁶

Therefore, powers of the legislative are provided under section 4 (8) of the 1999 Constitution as amended. The said Section, makes legislative power subject to the court’s jurisdiction. As can be seen under Section 4(8) of the 1999 constitution as amended which provides:

“Save as otherwise provided by this constitution, the exercise of legislative power by the national assembly or any of the house of assembly shall be subject to the jurisdiction of courts of law and of judicial tribunals established by law, and accordingly the national assembly or house of assembly shall not enact any law that purports to oust the jurisdiction of court of law or a judicial tribunal established by

²⁰. Ibid

²¹ Ibid.

²² Section 1, of the Military Government (Supremacy and Enforcement Powers) Decree No. 12 of 1994.

²³. A.G of Anambra State v. Okeke (1992) 1, NWLR, Pt.215, p. 60.

²⁴. Ibid at p. 86

²⁵ Section 6 (3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended.

²⁶. Ibid.

law.”²⁷

However, as the time goes on, coupled with the transformation of Nigeria from Military rule to the practicing the dictates of democracy the above section of law meant soften the old position of not allowing citizens to take action against the Government where it appear there was a violation of citizens’ rights.²⁸ In this regard, courts now have the powers to declare any act or law made by the legislative arms of government where it is inconsistent with the provision of the constitution.²⁹

A clear example can be seen in the case of A.G of Ondo State v. A.G. of Federation³⁰ where the Supreme Court held that, section 35 of the Corrupt Practices Act No. 4 of 2000, was unconstitutional for violating the right to personal liberty Nigerian citizens as enshrined under section 35 of the 1999 constitution of Nigeria.³¹

In this modern-day democracy of Nigeria, courts are now seen exercising the powers of making laws instead of interpreting the laws made by the legislative arms of government. This situation can scum with word of erudite justice Oputa JSC (as he then was) he observed that: Where law is left on the hands of those that have no activisms of it its life will be too short. In his attempt in achieving justice states:

“It is not readily realized how much the law comes into play and controls the day-to-day event in the life of the ordinary citizens. It is the law, with the law and by the law that, ordinary citizen moves, lives and has his being. In any activity, he meets with the law, or seeks the protection of the law. It is to the law he looks up for the determination and protection of his fundamental right and essentials liberties.”³²

To, further analyze the situation of attainment of justice in Nigeria, courts have always elucidating the efficacy of justice in their decisions and judgements in defending the natural law of the citizens, in their readiness of protecting and attainment of justice. In this paper, elucidate the readiness of Nigerian courts in protecting the rights of the citizens in attainment of justice regards shall be heard to various pronouncement of Nigerian judges is needed.

In substantiating the above, granting bail to a defendant in a capital offence, can be one of it, as it appears as per pats -Acholonu JCA, in Ogueri v. The State,³³

“It must not easily forgotten that, in a country that prides itself with democratic tents, liberty and law are twin concepts and are therefore inseparable. It is said that bail for any accused of murder is impossible. We must avoid been intellectually captured by shrine of formalism... sic.

Justice in the above case, has being seen justice to be operated in a democratic state

²⁷ . Section 4(8) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended.

²⁸ Supra at p. 6.

²⁹ . Section 1 (3) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended.

³⁰ . A.G. OF Ondo State v. A.G. of Federation (2002) 9 NWLR Pt. 772; at pg. 310; also A.G. of Abia State v. A.G. of Federation (2002) 6 NWLR pt. 763; at p. 264

³¹ . Section 35 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, as amended

³² . <https://www.google.com> in Dailaye D. A. available at www.google.com assessed on the 11/12/2024 around 7:49 am

³³ . Ogueri v. State (2002) 2 C.L.R., at pg. 24 para, A – Bavailable at www.google.com assessed on the 11/12/2024 around 7:49 am

particularly in Nigeria that, restrictions should not be place on any case where its boarders the right of an individual in any case before the court, placing restrictions amount to a denial of justice by the law of the land.³⁴

1.3.1 Relationship between Law and Justice in Nigeria

Basically, law in itself is a tool of justice, each single term is complementing each other in their intersect and meaning. Justice, is a concept which represent the symbol of law, to mean just and righteous deeds. In this era of technological advancement now adays, what is being administered through judicial processes some will assume it, not to be the law but, the result of it may sometime consider to be. Law, is what the law, statutes, rules and regulations says but, justice is the pronouncement made by Nigerian courts in relation of a matter or what the law itself. Here, both law and justice have a fundamental relationship in complementing one another.³⁵

The Doctrine of separation of powers between the arms of government which the judiciary to administer, the law of the land categorically, gives judiciary its power to adjudicate but, making laws is the duties of the legislative arms of government. Where law is defective, it cannot assume legislative functions for instance, in a murderer if he so wishes can confessed to his offence alleged to have committed before a police officer but, if it were before a magistrate, he will not even have the guard to confessed the crime where because, confession before a magistrate may led to the result of justice.³⁶ Justice and the law, their relationship is the ensuring of result which will benefit the society to live in peace and harmony through the work of judicial machineries i.e., courts.

Therefore, where the laws of a State remain un-altered causing hardships to the generality of the people of the country, the courts have no any constitutional or moral functions to deviate to the intent and purposes of the law but, to act according to the law as they are made by the Legislative Assembly. Law in that regard is blind and as a result, justice may also be blind.³⁷

The above assertion is in line with what was interpreted by the Supreme Court following the interpretation of the wording of Statute according to the intention of the legislators. As in the case of *R. v. Bangaza* where the Supreme court interpreted the provisions of Section 319 (2) of the criminal procedure code in accordance with the intention of the legislatures. The court in doing so, apply one of the principles of interpretation of statutes i.e., the literal rule in knowing the intention of the legislatures. The court applied the plain meaning of the word “age” to mean the age of conviction not the age for the commission of the offence.³⁸

Therefore, the courts in Nigeria, in their decision must apply the law as it is, as the Supreme court apply literal rule of interpretation in the case of *R. v Bangaza* cited above where the court therein have applied its rule even if the hardship would be resulted in applying literal rule of interpretation. This is to show that, what the law says is that, how the justice would be.

1.4 Conclusion

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/giss.v20i1.3> the concept of rule of law and the notion of justice in the survival of the Nigerian state; available at www.google.com assessed on the 12/12/2024 around 4: 44 pm.

³⁶ <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/giss.v20i1.3> the concept of rule of law and the notion of justice in the survival of the Nigerian state; available at www.google.com assessed on the 12/12/2024 around 4: 44 pm.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ *Rv. Bangaza* (1960)5 FSC P.1 <https://djetlawyer.com> available at www.google.com assessed on the 12/12/2024 around 8:51 pm.

Conclusively. “Law and justice” are terms used in the Nigerian legal system, the later is the result of the former, while, both the two (2) terms their meaning sometimes is so similar that, one term cannot establish itself without the help of the other. Law, is defined as a command as proposes by John Austin while, justice was defined as just or fair-play. The nature of law and justice in Nigeria, steam from the fact that, under military regime, whatever Decree says is final, the courts are bound to apply it whether there is justice in it or otherwise. Under military, ousting of constitutional provisions is the order of the day even if affect the rights of Nigerian citizens.

Consequently, where civil proceedings relate to the matters against the government those civil proceedings shall be stopped or where any provisions of the constitution or any other law which is in conflict with the provisions of the Decree or an Edict of a State government, that law shall be void with no effect. As observed in the case of *A.G. Anambra v. A.G. of Federation*; and *Okeke v. State*, as far Decree No. 13, of 1984. Once a Decree ousted courts’ jurisdiction the court is bound to act and apply.

Similarly, legislative powers cannot be exercised without interference of the judiciary, this means that, Doctrine of separation of power is attached to that of judicial control. Laws of Nigeria play vital roles in controlling and protecting rights of citizens. In Nigeria, legislators are the body saddled with the responsibilities of passing laws while judiciary ensures the justice of the case according to the intent and purposes of the legislators.

4.1.2 Findings

The paper found as follows:

1. Looking at the law and justice, under Military regime, the highest law of the land is the Military Decree. Unlike, in the Democratic state, where the constitution is the highest law of the land.
2. In a Democratic state, consultation is mandatory particular at the National or state Assembly i.e., debate of the law. While in a Military consultation is absent.
3. Doctrine of separation of power that, each tier of government shall perform its duties separately but, Section 4(8) of the 1999 the Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria subjected the legislative powers to the jurisdiction of the courts in order to find arbitrariness of powers given to the Legislators.
4. Both law and justice are serving one purpose of ensuring fundamental rights of Nigerians are fully protected against the abuse of public offers.

4.1.3 Recommendations

This paper recommends as follows:

1. Nigerians should ensure the observance of the dictates of the democratic system of government thereby, avoiding any attempt which might bring Military to take over the affairs of the State.
2. Separation of powers should be maintained particularly; the judiciary should not subject the functions and duties of the legislative arms of government unless with cogent and compelling reasons so to do.
3. Nigerian laws should be enacted purposely in achieving justice, fairness to Nigerians, rigorous provisions of laws should be amended.